

Social Media Usage and Academic Procrastination Among Students Pursuing Higher Education

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Introduction:

Social media can be defined as forms of electronic communication through which users interact among people in which they create, freely share, exchange and discuss information, ideas, personal messages, and other content about each other and their lives using a multimedia mix of personal words, pictures, videos and audio, utilizing online platforms while they are connected to the Internet (Cox & Rothmans, 2011). According to (Smith 2010), "Social media sites are virtual platforms for interactivity and information exchange where issues are debated and defined. Social media users collaborate in content creation, are proactive in searching information and value control in social media participation (Kaplan & Heinlein, 2010) social media are also defined as "a group of Internet-based applications that build on the ideological and technological foundations of Web 2.0 and that allow the creation and exchange of user generated content."

Advantages & Disadvantages of Social Networking:

Advantages:

- ✓ Facilitates open communication, leading to enhanced information discovery and delivery.
- ✓ Allows employees to discuss ideas, post news, ask questions and share links.
- ✓ Provides an opportunity to widen business contacts.
- ✓ Targets a wide audience, making it a useful and effective recruitment tool.
- ✓ Improves business reputation and client base with minimal use of advertising.
- ✓ Expands market research, implements marketing campaigns, delivers communications and directs interested people to specific web sites.

Disadvantages:

- ✓ Opens up the possibility for hackers to commit fraud and launch spam and virus attacks.
- ✓ Increases the risk of people falling prey to online scams that seem genuine, resulting in data or identity theft.
- ✓ Potentially results in negative comments from employees about the company or potential legal consequences if employees use these sites to view objectionable, illicit or offensive material.
- ✓ Potentially results in lost productivity, especially if employees are busy updating profiles, etc.

Types of Social Networking Sites

There is an innumerable number of social networking sites empowered with various technological affordances. Besides, the cultures that emerge around these sites are varied. In this study ten major Social Networking Sites have been identified for a brief explanation. These include: Facebook, Orkut, Google plus, Myspace, Bharatstudent, Hi5, Twitter, Ibibio, Classmates.com and Friendster.

1. **Facebook:** Facebook is the most popular and frequently used social networking site. It is basically an online social networking site which derives its name from the colloquial name for the book given to students at the start of the academic year by some American university administrations to help them to get to know each other. Facebook was founded in February 2004 by Mark Zuckerberg with his college roommates and fellow Harvard University students, Eduardo Saverin, Andrew McCollum, Dustin Moskovitz and Chris Hughes.

2. **Orkut:** Orkut is a social networking site which is owned and operated by Google. The service is designed to help users meet new and old friends and maintain existing relationships. Orkut is available in 48. languages throughout the world enabling increased usage. The website is named after its creator, Google employee Orkut Büyükkökten. It is noteworthy that Orkut is one of the most visited websites in India and Brazil. As of October 2011, 59.1% of Orkut's users were from Brazil, followed by India with 27.1% and Japan with 6.7%. As of October 2012, Alexa traffic ranked Orkut.com 746th and Orkut.com.br 738th in the world; the web site currently has over 33 million active users worldwide.
3. **Google Plus:** Google Plus is another social networking and identity service that is owned and operated by Google Inc. It is the second-largest social networking site in the world, having surpassed Twitter in January 2017. It has approximately 359 million active users. As of May 2017, it had a total of 500 million registered users, of whom 235 million are active in a given month. Google has described Google+ as a "social layer" that enhances many of its online properties, unlike conventional social networks generally accessed through a single website.
4. **Myspace:** Myspace is a social networking site with a strong music emphasis which is owned by Specific Media LLC and pop music singer and actor Justin Timberlake. Myspace was launched in August 2003 and is headquartered in Beverly Hills, California. In June 2012, Myspace had 25 million unique U.S. visitors. In 2013 there are 50 million users of this site. Myspace was founded in 2003 and was acquired by News Corporation in July 2005 for \$580 million. From 2005 until early 2008, Myspace was the most visited social networking site in the world, and in June 2006 it surpassed Google as the most visited website in the United States. In April 2008, Myspace was overtaken by Facebook in the number of unique worldwide visitors, and outshone the number of unique U.S. visitors in May 2009. Myspace generated \$800 million in revenue during the 2008 fiscal year. Since then, the number of Myspace users has declined steadily in spite of several redesigns. As of June 2018, Myspace was ranked 303 by total web traffic and 223 in the United States.
5. **Twitter:** Twitter is an online Social Networking Site with micro blogging service that enables users to send and read "tweets", which are text messages limited to 140 characters. Registered users can read and post tweets while unregistered users can only read them. Users access Twitter through the website interface, SMS, or mobile device app. Twitter Inc. is based in San Francisco and has offices in New York City, Boston, San Antonio and Detroit. As such Twitter was created in March 2006 by Jack Dorsey, Evan Williams, Biz Stone and Noah Glass and by July 2006, the site was launched. The service rapidly gained worldwide popularity, with 500 million registered users in 2018, who posted 340 million tweets per day. The service also handled 1.6 billion search queries per day. Twitter is now one of the ten most visited websites, and has been described as "the SMS of the Internet."

Rationale of the Study

Social media has a great influence in student's life. Surveys show that 90 % of teens are using social media. Studies show that increased use of social media affecting adolescents' psychosocial well-being. In recent years the use of internet and social media increased rapidly. Social media include websites and applications that allow users to share content, ideas, opinions, beliefs, feelings, and their personal, social and educational experiences. They also allow communication among a wide range of users at global level. More than 4.5 billion people are using the internet at the start of 2020, active social media users have passed the 3.8 billion mark with this number increasing by more than 9 percent (321 million new users) since this time last year. Social media plays a big role in teens culture today. There are plenty of positive aspects of social media, but significant risks in the excessive use to be addressed.

Adolescents are among the most enthusiastic users of social networking and social media. The present study examines how the usage of social media affects self-esteem and academic procrastination in adolescent group. The increased number of technological applications gives opportunities to the adolescence to connect,

communicate, and interact with each other. However, this use raises an important question for educational and developmental psychologists; how does social media affected academic procrastination?

Research Problem

The present research aims to study the influence of social media in adolescents' self-esteem and academic procrastination.

Objectives

- 1.To assess the social media usage in students pursuing higher education.
- 2.To study the relationship between social media usage and academic procrastination in students pursuing higher education

Hypothesis

- 1.There is a significant relationship between social media usage and academic procrastination among adolescents.

Operational Definitions

Social Media: social media is a computer-based technology that facilitate the sharing of ideas, thoughts, and information through the building of virtual networks and communities.

Adolescence: Adolescence is a psycho-socio-biological stage of development occurring between childhood and adulthood. During this period, rapid and important developments occur which give rise to the need for adjustment and the necessity for establishing new attitudes, values and interests (Elizabeth Hurlock, 1968).

Procrastination: Procrastination comes from the Latin pro, meaning "forward, forth, or in favor of," and crustiness, meaning "of tomorrow". Procrastination is defined as the act off or delaying an action to a later time (Bachrach,2012).

Delimitation

- The study was limited to Pandharpur city only.
- The study was delimited to 100 students pursuing higher education of different colleges of Solapur district.
- The study was further delimited to students of age group 18 to 23 years only.

Sample

The sample represents the population the researcher wants to study. A sample of 100 students pursuing higher education from different college in Solapur district is selected using purposive sampling technique. The age group of the students was 18 to 23 years.

Research Design

Research design is the framework of methods and techniques adopted to collect measure and analyses data. It provides the researcher an understanding on how to proceed with the research and the methodology to be used.it is an answer to the different question related to the study. In the present study, a co-relational research design is used to study the relationship between social media usage and academic procrastination among adolescence.

Tests And Tools

1. Tuckman Procrastination Scale (TPS)
2. Social Media Addiction Scale Student Form (SMAS SF).

Statistical Analysis

Descriptive and inferential statistics was used. Appropriate statistical analysis was done to find out the correlation between the variables and differences among the group based on the nature of the data. Pearson Product Moment Correlation was used for the present study.

Tabulation is essential because of the following reasons:

1. It conserves space and reduces explanatory and descriptive statement to a minimum.
2. Its facilities the summation of items and the detection of errors and omissions.
3. Its facilities the process of comparison.
4. It provides a basis for various statistical computations.

Table 1: Demographic profile of students pursuing higher education

S.I. No.	Variables	Categories	Percentage
1.	Gender	Male	50%
		female	50%
2.	Educational Qualification	Secondary	50%
		Senior secondary	50%
3.	Religion of student	Hindus	52%
		Muslim	36%
		Christians	12%
		Others	0%
4.	No. of sibling	1	88%
		2	12%
		3	0%
5	Birth Order	First born	55%
		Second Born	40%
		Later Born	5%

❖ Duration of social media among students

Table 2: Duration of social media Among Adolescent

Duration	Frequency	Percentage
3-4 hour	25	25
4-5 hours	40	40
More than 5 hours	35	35
Total	100	100

Table 3 shows the duration of social media addiction by the respondent. 25% of the distance learner use smartphone 3 to 4 hour, 40% of them use 4 to 5 hours and 35% of them use more than 5 hours a day.

Testing Of Hypotheses

Hypothesis 1: There is a significant relationship between social media usage and academic procrastination among students pursuing higher education.

Pearson Product Moment Correlation analysis is used to find out the strength of relationship between social media usage and academic procrastination among students pursuing higher education.

Table 3: Correlation Among Social Media Usage and Academic Procrastination Among Students Pursuing Higher Education

Variables	N	Correlation	Significance
Social Media Usage	100	0.179**	**P<0.01
Academic Procrastination			

****Significant at 0.01 level**

Conclusion

Social media has a very strong impact on the self-esteem of individuals. Students use these social networking sites for information, communication and building and maintain relationships. But majority of the people end up making upward and downward comparisons with others. The upward comparisons make people envy others and their lifestyles and also feel less obliged and ungrateful for their bounties. As a result the self-esteem of such people gets negatively affected. Social media is growing very drastically in almost every country in the world.

After analyzing the relationship of social networking usage with academic procrastination among university students, the results revealed that there exists a statistically significant relationship between social networking usage and academic procrastination.

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